

The Relationship Between Form Four Examination Performance and Academic Outcomes in Health Sciences Non-Degree Programs in Health Training Institutions in Tanzania

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Abstract

This study explores the relationship between Form Four examination performance and academic success in health sciences non-degree programs in Tanzania. Using a quantitative correlational research design, it involved 54 tutors and 308 students from various health training institutions in Mbeya. Findings show that while Form Four examination performance is a significant predictor of academic success in health sciences non-degree programs, it is not the sole determinant of student outcomes. The findings reveal that other critical factors—such as personal commitment, study habits, teaching quality, and institutional support—also play pivotal roles in shaping academic performance. While 71.1% of students had strong secondary school results (Division I or II), 64.2% achieved a GPA of 3.1 or higher at the college level, indicating that motivation and study habits can compensate for weaker entry qualifications. Correlation analysis reveals strong relationships between motivation, study habits ($r = 0.942$), and teaching quality ($r = 0.855$). Form Four results correlated moderately with college success ($r = 0.538$ to 0.492 , $p < 0.001$), while institutional support alone showed weaker predictive power. The study also discusses the debate on raising entry qualifications, with 59.3% of tutors and 80.5% of students supporting the change, while others stress the importance of motivation and institutional support. It is recommended that health training institutions adopt a balanced admission approach that considers both academic qualifications and non-academic factors such as motivation and study habits. Additionally, enhancing academic resources, faculty development, and student support systems is essential to producing competent healthcare professionals.

Introduction

Currently, around the world, many countries are facing the problem of unemployment, especially among graduates from colleges and universities. In their report [1] state that the unemployment rate has consistently been a major concern for graduates over the years and that every day, thousands of students successfully complete their studies at both public and private higher education institutions. However, studies show that in African countries, the problem is particularly severe. For instance [2] explains that graduate unemployment has become a very serious challenge in Africa, where,

among the 10 million graduates produced by 668 universities, half of them fail to secure employment. This indicates that graduate unemployment is one of the most critical developmental challenges facing the African continent. In our view, aside from other challenges, we believe that this issue may stem from the increased enrollment of students from primary to tertiary education levels, resulting in institutions producing more graduates than the available job market can absorb, particularly for office-based employment. [3] confirm that, with universal primary education and rapid increases in secondary school

More Information

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enrollment policies, school enrollment rates have dramatically increased in almost all developing countries since the 1960s. Given this prevailing situation in many countries, it is evident that competition in the job market has become very intense, with good academic performance being considered a key criterion in the entire recruitment process for various positions in institutions and companies globally. In this regard, [3] emphasize the crucial role of education in shaping labor market outcomes for young people and highlight the need for renewed focus on investing in quality education at all levels, from pre-primary through tertiary, as a key priority in the development agenda.

Additionally, the pressure to invest in quality education has significantly influenced the admission criteria for students aspiring to join higher education institutions. [4] support the view that the increase in the number of colleges and universities in many countries in recent years has necessitated a reevaluation of the criteria for assessing education. Quality is undoubtedly the foremost criterion that comes to mind. This has led to a focus on contributing to human development and career skills, attracting highly qualified students, enhancing institutional status, and positioning universities as key social institutions in their countries. Therefore, in this regard, admissions to colleges and universities in many countries, including Tanzania, now often prioritize applicants with strong academic performance at lower education levels, based on the belief that high-performing applicants are likely to excel academically in college and are more likely to graduate with good academic results.

Unlike other sectors, ensuring excellent academic performance in the admission of students into health science programs has been given priority. This may be due to the perception of its sensitivity, as it deals with human life and requires individuals with exceptional intellectual abilities to produce competent professionals who meet the demands of the job market, unlike other disciplines. [5] support this, noting that medicine is one of the most sought-after careers worldwide, with access to medical schools being highly competitive. Consequently, admission criteria, such as the type of high school diploma, academic grades, and admission pathways, are significant predictors of graduation likelihood and the final GPA of medical students. Hence, with the growing number of applicants and the significant changes in teaching and assessment methods in these colleges, continuous evaluation and refinement of admission criteria are essential [6].

In the context of Tanzania's healthcare system, which relies heavily on a workforce of skilled professionals, many of whom are trained through certificate-level programs in health sciences, the significance of these

programs cannot be overstated. Programs such as nursing, pharmacy, and clinical medicine play a pivotal role in preparing healthcare workers who serve as the backbone of the health sector, particularly in rural and underserved regions. Ensuring that health-related programs produce competent and adequately skilled professionals is essential due to their significant contributions to national health outcomes. A review of the NACTVET Admission Guidebook for 2024/2025 reveals that the entry requirements for health-related programs recognized as National Technical Awards (NTAs) are notably higher compared to those for other non-health allied science programs [7]. Similarly, scholars such as [8] emphasize that health systems face significant challenges, particularly in low-income countries with greater health needs, rapid population growth, and limited healthcare resources. Modern technology has increased the potential for cross-country learning, but this process extends beyond knowledge transfer—it requires adaptation, negotiation, and internalization. Despite its complexity, the benefits to health systems are substantial. Key elements of learning in health policy include the individuals involved in learning, the subject matter, and the anticipated impact on policy changes. Therefore, enhancing the skills of health professionals and strengthening institutions in low- and middle-income countries are crucial for addressing health challenges and achieving sustainable improvements through workforce training, comprehensive education programs, and leadership development [9].

In Tanzania, concerns have emerged about the academic performance of students admitted to diploma health science programs, particularly those with lower Form Four examination scores. Regulatory bodies and educational stakeholders argue that students with weak academic backgrounds often struggle to meet the rigorous demands of health science training. This results in high failure and low completion rates, hindering individual aspirations and threatening the quality and supply of healthcare professionals in the country. In this view, proposals have been made to raise entry qualifications ordinary diploma in health science programs to improve academic outcomes. On the other hand, critics caution that such measures could unintentionally limit access for aspiring healthcare professionals, particularly those from low-income families or remote rural areas. This underscores the need for a balanced approach that maintains accessibility while enhancing student success. However, to date, there is no scientific evidence to support the claim for increasing the admission requirements for these health programs. To address these gaps, this study will pursue two key objectives: first, to evaluate the academic performance of students in health training programs based on their

Form Four examination results; second, to analyze the relationship between Form Four grades and other influencing factors related to academic success into ordinary diploma in health science programs.

Moreover, the rationale for this study is to provide evidence-based insights that can guide admission policies and develop strategies to support student success. Additionally, the research aims to contribute to the broader discourse on creating an equitable and high-quality health education system that effectively serves Tanzania’s diverse population. By engaging with existing theories and empirical findings, the study seeks to bridge the gap between policy debates and the lived experiences of students in health science programs.

Methods and Materials

This study employed a quantitative correlational research design to investigate the relationship between Form Four examination performance (independent variable) and academic outcomes in health sciences non-degree programs (dependent variable). According to [10], a correlational design is used to examine the relationships between or among two or more variables within a single group, which can occur at several levels. This design allows researchers to explore relationships without manipulating or controlling any variables. It also reflects the strength and direction of the relationship between variables, which can be either positive or negative. Cohen, Manion, and Morrison (2000) explain that correlational techniques are designed to address three key questions about the relationship between two variables or data sets. The first question seeks to determine whether a relationship exists between the two variables (or data sets). The second question examines the direction of the relationship (whether it is positive or negative). The third question explores the magnitude of the relationship (the strength or degree of correlation). By utilizing this design, the study aims to provide a clear understanding of how Form Four examination performance relates to academic outcomes in health sciences non-degree programs.

The study involved 54 tutors from Health Sciences Training Institutions and 308 students, comprising 167 NTA Level 5 and 141 NTA Level 6 students in Mbeya region. These students were enrolled in various health sciences non-degree programs, including Nursing, Pharmacy, Clinical Medicine, Dentistry, Medical Laboratory Science, Radiology, Anesthesia, and Health Information Science. The participants were drawn from nine out of ten Health Sciences Training Colleges in the Mbeya region. The study utilized a questionnaire as the sole method of data collection for both tutors and students. According to [11], a questionnaire is a data collection instrument consisting of a structured series of written questions that respondents answer independently, without the researcher present, to

gather information on their opinions, beliefs, feelings, interests, expectations, and experiences. The collected data were analyzed quantitatively using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 23 (IBM corporation). Research ethics were carefully adhered to throughout the study, including obtaining research clearance from the Teofilo Kisanji University Research Committee and the Mbeya Regional Government Authority. Additionally, the principles of informed consent, anonymity, and confidentiality were strictly observed. This has been emphasized by [12] that, ethical norms underpin societal laws and research practices, though ethics and law are not the same. An action may be lawful yet unethical or unlawful yet ethical. Adherence to ethical principles in research is crucial to safeguard integrity by ensuring knowledge, truth, and accuracy while preventing misconduct like data falsification. Ethical standards also promote trust, accountability, respect, and fairness, essential for collaboration among researchers from diverse disciplines and institutions, ensuring credible research outcomes.

Results and Discussion

Academic Performance of Students in Health Training Programs Based on their Form Four examination results

This section presents and discusses data related to the first objective, which focused on evaluating the academic performance of students in health training programs based on their Form Four examination results, with the following subsections.

Students' Academic Performance in the Form Four Examination

Under this subsection, the researchers aimed to examine the overall Form Four National examination results of the students involved in this study, as indicated by the responses in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Overall Academic Performance of Students in the Form Four National Examination

Category	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
Division I	81	26.3
Division II	138	44.8
Division III	59	19.2
Division IV	30	9.7
TOTAL	308	100

Source: Field Data (2024)

For instance, the data in Table 1 show that the majority of students performed relatively well, with 71.1% (219 out of 308 respondents) achieving Division I or II. This indicates that most students entering health sciences programs had strong academic abilities. However, on the other hand, 28.9% (89 students) attained Division III or IV, suggesting that some students who joined

health sciences programs had weaker academic backgrounds in secondary school. This, to some extent, may affect their ability to cope with the rigorous nature of health sciences programs.

For admission into health sciences programs for NTAs levels in Tanzania, student performance in five key secondary school subjects—Biology, Chemistry, Physics, Mathematics, and English Language—is considered. In the Tanzanian context, these admission criteria closely align with those proposed in Saudi

Arabia, as mentioned by [6]. According to their study, the scientific track is designed for students aspiring to pursue fields such as Medicine, Dentistry, Nursing, or Applied Medical Sciences. This track includes core subjects such as Mathematics, Chemistry, Biology, Physics, Communication Skills, Computing and Information Technology, and Academic English. The distribution of grades among students in this study is shown in table 2 below.

Table 2. Secondary School Academic Performance by Subject

Subject	Grade A	%	Grade B	%	Grade C	%	Grade D	%	Grade F	%
Biology	52	16.90	112	36.40	118	38.30	25	8.10	1	0.30
Chemistry	40	13.00	91	29.50	136	44.20	38	12.30	3	1.00
Physics	25	8.10	49	15.90	72	23.40	120	39.00	42	13.60
Mathematics	31	10.10	46	14.90	84	27.30	105	34.10	42	13.60
English Language	72	23.40	80	26.00	104	33.80	46	14.90	6	1.90

Source: Field Data (2024)

The data indicated in Table 2 provides important insights into the academic performance of students in the five key secondary school subjects considered for admission into health sciences programs. According to [6], in medical and health science schools, selecting the right students is a complex challenge that requires multiple prerequisites and careful consideration. To ensure the admission of highly qualified candidates who are more likely to succeed in the field, pre-admission criteria have been implemented in medical schools and health sciences colleges worldwide. These criteria often include academic achievements, such as cumulative high school scores and standardized achievement tests designed to assess the knowledge acquired during the final years of secondary education. The consideration of key criteria for students enrolling in health science programs is very important because the academic performance of a medical student attracts the attention of medical professionals [13].

In this study, the data in Table 2 shows that most students scored C or higher in Biology, Chemistry, and English Language. This indicates that they have a solid foundation in subjects directly relevant to health sciences, as well as a good understanding of the English language, which is crucial for grasping medical terminologies and coursework delivered in English. However, in Physics and Mathematics, a significant number of students earned D or F grades (Physics: 52.6%, Mathematics: 47.7%). These figures highlight that many students have weaknesses in these subjects, which can present challenges, especially in courses that require strong analytical and problem-solving skills. According to [14], a comprehensive understanding of physics concepts requires proficiency in the

mathematical language that underpins these concepts. However, many students in introductory, algebra-based physics courses struggle with mathematical problem-solving tasks in physics. There are at least two distinct possible reasons for this poor performance: (1) students may lack the necessary mathematical skills to solve physics problems, or (2) students may possess the required mathematical skills but do not know how to effectively apply them to specific problem situations in physics. In addition [15] and [16] highlight the lasting impact of higher-level secondary school mathematics on university academic performance, from entry through to the completion of a certificate, diploma, or degree. Advanced mathematics fosters essential skills such as problem-solving, logical reasoning, and error detection, which are crucial for success in tertiary education confirming that a stronger foundation in mathematics leads to better academic outcomes. Furthermore, the level of mathematics studied before university (directly from secondary school) significantly influences first-year performance. Based on these findings, we conclude that students with weaker backgrounds in Mathematics and Physics may face challenges in the quantitative aspects of their training, including dosage calculations, diagnostic imaging, and laboratory measurements.

Students’ Academic Performance Progress in College

The academic performance progress in college is presented in the form of Grade Point Averages (GPAs) for First-Year Semester Two Ministry Examination Results (NTA Level 5), First-Year Semester Two Ministry Examination Results (NTA Level 6), and Second-Year Semester Two Ministry Examination Results (NTA Level 6), as shown in Table 3 below.

Table 3. Academic Performance Progress of Students at Different NTA Levels Based on GPA Ranges

Level	GPA Range	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
NTA Level 5	3.5 - 4.0 (Very Good)	141	45.80%
	3.0 - 3.4 (Good)	128	41.60%
	2.5 - 2.9 (Fair)	38	12.30%
	< 2.5 (Poor)	1	0.30%
NTA Level 6 (Year 1)	3.5 - 4.0 (Very Good)	92	29.90%
	3.0 - 3.4 (Good)	63	20.50%
	2.5 - 2.9 (Fair)	9	2.90%
	< 2.5 (Poor)	0	0.00%
NTA Level 6 (Year 2)	3.5 - 4.0 (Very Good)	86	27.90%
	3.0 - 3.4 (Good)	64	20.80%
	2.5 - 2.9 (Fair)	10	3.20%
	< 2.5 (Poor)	0	0.00%

Source: Field Data (2024)

The data presented and analyzed in Table 3 illustrate the academic performance of students in health programs at the college level, from NTA Level 5 to NTA Level 6 (Year One and Year Two), based on their GPA ranges. The results provide valuable insights into the distribution of student performance across different levels, highlighting trends in academic achievement. For instance, at NTA Level 5, which is the entry-level stage, student performance appears to be strong, with 45.8% achieving a Very Good GPA (3.5 - 4.0) and 41.6% attaining a Good GPA (3.0 - 3.4). This suggests that the majority of students in NTA Level 5 demonstrated strong academic performance, with nearly 87.4% scoring at least a GPA of 3.0 or above. However, 12.3% of students fell into the Fair category (2.5 - 2.9), while a very small fraction (0.3%) performed poorly (<2.5). Comparing the percentages indicating good performance with those showing poor performance, it is evident that most students at this level had a solid academic foundation, with only a few struggling academically. In our view, this strong academic performance is likely attributed to the learning principle of progressing from simple to complex, which is applied across various educational levels. At the early stages, teaching is conducted using a simplified approach and basic content, making it easier for a larger number of students to grasp and excel in the subjects being taught. In this regard, [17] emphasizes that, when preparing learning materials for newcomers, the content should be sequenced in a way that facilitates a smooth progression from simple to more complex topics. This structured approach ensures a gradual build-up of knowledge, allowing learners to develop a strong foundation before tackling more advanced concepts. Notably, this is one of the few principles on which most educators widely agree. [18] confirm that education is structured in various stages

or levels, with each level building upon the previous one by providing deeper insights and elaboration on key components. At the first level, content is introduced in a broad overview, outlining the fundamental concepts of a lesson. In the second level, the content is further developed and organized based on the foundational knowledge presented in the first level. This progressive approach continues, with each subsequent level adding more depth and complexity until the desired level of understanding is achieved. On the other hand, unlike NTA Level 5, students' academic performance in NTA Level 6 Year One showed a slight decline. The percentage of students in the Very Good category (3.5 - 4.0) dropped to 29.9%, while those in the Good category (3.0 - 3.4) decreased to 20.5%. Additionally, 2.9% of students had Fair performance (2.5 - 2.9), while none scored below 2.5. This decline in performance at this higher level, compared to the initial NTA Level 5, may be attributed to the increased academic demands at this stage. Factors such as greater course complexity, a heavier workload, or other academic challenges could have contributed to this shift. [19] highlight that as students progress to higher levels, those who initially performed well tend to experience a faster decline in academic performance compared to those who started at lower levels, with only a few managing to maintain consistently high performance. This decline is influenced by motivational and cognitive factors, as academic success requires both effort and the ability to manage increasing cognitive demands. As students progress to higher levels, the curriculum demands greater independence, which may challenge their self-discipline. The complexity of skills required at advanced levels further adds to the cognitive burden, making it difficult for some students to sustain their performance. Additionally, [20] asserts that, during their second year

(middle class) of enrollment, students often question their academic direction, especially if they entered the institution without a predetermined major. Without a clear roadmap, they may feel lost and uncertain about their path. This uncertainty can lead them to enroll in courses that exceed their intellectual or cognitive abilities, further exacerbating their struggles. Second-year (middle class) students are often the 'forgotten cohort,' as they are assumed to have successfully transitioned from high school to college. But, many still face significant challenges in navigating their academic journey. [21] emphasizes that the end of the second year (middle class) can be a critical juncture where students may interrupt their progress toward graduation. During this period, they may exhibit behaviors such as prolonged indecisiveness, poor course selection, low levels of academic and co-curricular engagement, integration difficulties, behavioral issues, and an extended time to degree completion.

However, academic performance at NTA Level 6 from Year 2 to Year 3 showed slight improvement compared to Year 1. The proportion of students in the Very Good category (3.5 - 4.0) was 27.9%, while those in the Good category (3.0 - 3.4) slightly increased to 20.8%. Meanwhile, 3.2% of students fell in the Fair range (2.5 - 2.9), and no students scored below 2.5. This improvement may be attributed to time management, maturity in academics and the reduced number of courses as students approach the end of their programs. In comparison to the middle of their studies, when there are more courses with higher academic demands affected with poor time management, the fewer courses towards the end allow students more time to study, which likely gives them a better opportunity to perform well. [22] emphasize that, consistent and active study habits were the most common reasons senior college students cited for their academic success. Additionally, setting clear goals, maintaining a conducive study environment, and effective time management were also considered key factors. Conversely, academic failure in the middle classes was primarily attributed to insufficient study, poor time management, and inadequate goal-setting. Moreover [20] highlights that, many colleges and departments do not provide structured academic

advising until the third year or once students have earned enough credits to complete their general education and prerequisite requirements.

Therefore, the improvement in academic performance from Year 1 to Year 2 at NTA Level 6 reflects the impact of academic maturity, better time management, and a lighter course load. However, the challenges of the middle years, marked by heavier academic demands and limited structured advising, highlight the need for early intervention strategies to support student success.

To conclude this subsection, we comprehend that, the observed trends in academic performance across NTA Level 5 and NTA Level 6 underscore the importance of progressive learning strategies, effective time management, and the ability to adapt to increasing academic demands. As students move through different levels, they face heightened cognitive challenges that require greater self-discipline and motivation to maintain high performance. The improvement seen in Year 2 of NTA Level 6 suggests that with maturity and refined study habits, students can navigate these challenges successfully. In due course, this discussion highlights the crucial role of structured learning and academic resilience in achieving sustained academic success.

Correlation Between Form Four National Examination Results and College Academic Performance

In this section, the researchers aimed to investigate the extent of the correlation between Form Four grades and other factors influencing academic success in ordinary diploma programs in health sciences, including examining whether there is a need to increase the minimum entry qualifications for these programs. Data were presented and discussed as follows.

The relationship between Form Four grades and other influencing factors related to academic success into ordinary diploma in health science programs

The bivariate correlation analysis reveals significant positive relationships between all factors influencing students' academic success. All correlations are statistically significant at the $p < 0.01$ level, indicating strong confidence in these relationships. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) as it is indicated in Table 4 below.

Table 4. Correlation Matrix of Academic Performance Factors

Item	Form Four Academic Performance	Teaching Quality	Study Habits	Institutional Support (e.g., Library, Tutoring)	Personal Commitment and Motivation
Form Four Academic Performance	1	.529**	.538**	.492**	.518**
Teaching Quality	.529**	1	.827**	.760**	.855**
Study Habits	.538**	.827**	1	.755**	.942**

Institutional Support (e.g., Library, Tutoring)	.492**	.760**	.755**	1	.778**
Personal Commitment and Motivation	.518**	.855**	.942**	.778**	1

Source: Field Data (2024)

The data from Table 4 highlights significant relationships between Form Four grades and other factors affecting academic success in health science diploma programs. Key factors such as Personal Commitment and Motivation, Study Habits, Teaching Quality, Institutional Support, and Academic Performance play a crucial role in students' success. The strongest correlation is observed between Personal Commitment and Motivation and Study Habits ($r = 0.942, p < 0.001$), suggesting that motivated students are more likely to develop structured and disciplined study habits, ultimately enhancing their academic performance. Similarly, Teaching Quality shows strong correlations with Personal Commitment and Motivation ($r = 0.855, p < 0.001$), Study Habits ($r = 0.827, p < 0.001$), and Institutional Support ($r = 0.760, p < 0.001$), indicating that high-quality instruction fosters student engagement, disciplined learning behaviors, and access to academic resources. In terms of direct academic achievement, Form Four Academic Performance exhibits moderate correlations with Study Habits ($r = 0.538, p < 0.001$), Teaching Quality ($r = 0.529, p < 0.001$), and Personal Commitment and Motivation ($r = 0.518, p < 0.001$), reinforcing the idea that structured learning strategies, high-quality instruction, and intrinsic motivation significantly influence long-term academic success. However, Institutional Support shows the weakest correlation with Form Four Academic Performance ($r = 0.492, p < 0.001$), suggesting that while access to academic resources is beneficial, personal motivation and study habits play a more decisive role in sustaining high academic achievement. Notably, Institutional Support demonstrates strong correlations with Personal Commitment and Motivation ($r = 0.778, p < 0.001$), Teaching Quality ($r = 0.760, p < 0.001$), and Study Habits ($r = 0.755, p < 0.001$), highlighting the importance of well-equipped academic environments in reinforcing student motivation and learning behaviors. In a nutshell, this data emphasizes that student motivation, study habits, and teaching quality are the primary drivers of academic success for health science students in training colleges. Motivated students naturally develop effective study routines, and while past performance and institutional support matter, personal effort and quality teaching have a greater impact on student achievement.

These findings align with observations reported from various countries, including Ethiopia, Somalia, Nigeria, and Saudi Arabia, on factors affecting health science

students' academic performance in health training colleges. Studies by [23], [24], [25] and [26] support the results of this study. In their study, they identified four major factors influencing students' academic performance, including teacher-related factors (such as a good relationship with students and co-teachers, teachers' mastery of subject matter, the use of teaching aids/devices and effective teaching techniques, and classroom management), college-related factors (such as physical requirements like classroom size, lighting, noise environment, internet access in the library, water supply, electricity, playing ground, staff offices, and hostels), student-related factors (such as listening to the teacher, a desire for good grades on quizzes, assignments, and exams, and regularly completing assignments and studying habits), and home-related factors (such as having a clean, orderly, and designated study space at home, parental background and other home-related issues). Additionally, Khan et al. (2020) identified several factors influencing the academic performance of medical students, including parental involvement, time spent on social media, peer influence, study environment, and teaching style. Moreover, they found a significant association between academic performance and factors such as place of residence, daily breakfast consumption, peer academic performance, night study habits, and the decision to pursue a medical career based on personal interest. Indeed, a student's academic success in higher education begins with personal effort. An individual may enter college with average secondary school results, but with a strong sense of responsibility and clear aspirations, they can achieve outstanding success—even surpassing those who had excellent secondary school results. According to [27] academically engaged students tend to comply with school demands, such as attendance and discipline, which enables them to achieve overall academic success and overcome academic challenges. On the other hand, disengaged students are more likely to skip classes, develop a negative attitude toward their academic institutions, and often underperform. Furthermore, [4] emphasize that, for medical trainees, academic success is determined by personal competence, which is the thoughtful and effective use of communication, knowledge, technical skills, clinical reasoning, and emotional intelligence in daily practice for the benefit of individuals and communities. It builds upon fundamental clinical skills, scientific knowledge, and ethical development, encompassing cognitive

abilities to solve problems, integrative skills for reasoning, relational skills for effective communication, and emotional awareness for the humane application of these skills. Competence is shaped by critical thinking, curiosity, self-awareness, and professional presence, and it is developmental, evolving with experience and adapting to the context of medical practice. In tandem, all these factors play a crucial role in shaping students' academic success.

Therefore, based on these major factors influencing college students' academic achievement, we believe there is sufficient evidence that Form Four results alone cannot solely determine a student's success in health science programs. A student's academic success in

health science college is built upon various other crucial factors. However, good Form Four results will remain an essential and fundamental requirement for a student's academic progress in higher education.

Increasing Minimum Entry Qualifications

After examining the extent of the correlation between Form Four grades and other factors influencing academic success in ordinary diploma programs in health sciences, researchers sought to understand from both respondents (tutors and students) whether there is a need to increase the minimum entry qualifications for these programs. Their responses are presented in Table 5 below as follows.

Table 5. Perceptions on Increasing Minimum Entry Qualifications

Respondent Group	Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Tutors	Yes	32	59.30%
	No	15	27.80%
	Not Sure	7	13.00%
Total		54	100%
Students	Yes	248	80.50%
	No	60	19.50%
Total		308	100%

Source: Field Data (2024)

Based on the data collected from both tutors and students, as presented in Table 5, there are mixed perceptions regarding the impact of increasing minimum entry qualifications on academic performance in health programs. However, the majority of respondents, support raising the entry requirements for ordinary diploma programs in health sciences. Specifically, 59.3% of tutors and 80.5% of students believe that higher Form Four grades would enhance academic outcomes. This strong support, underscores the widespread belief that academic preparedness is a key factor in achieving success in health-related studies. [28] supports these results that, academic achievement is a significant indicator in many developing countries, including Tanzania, where it is primarily measured through final examinations, such as the Form Four National Examination. Success is determined by academic performance and how well students meet the standards set by the National Examination Council of Tanzania (NECTA) and individual institutions. Performance at the secondary school level plays a crucial role in shaping students' success in higher and tertiary education.

According to [29] one of the most significant risk factors consistently identified in the literature is students' intellectual ability to cope with the academic demands of university studies. Their findings emphasize the importance of students' competence and academic performance background, suggesting that those with a strong academic foundation are more likely to excel in

university. Likewise, students who perform well in university are more likely to complete their studies and graduate successfully, whereas those who struggle academically face a higher risk of not finishing their programs. In this regard, [30] emphasize that a nation's social and economic development is closely linked to the quality of its universities and the academic performance of its students. Hence, it is believed that, Students' academic performance plays a crucial role in producing high-quality graduates who become future leaders and a skilled workforce, contributing to a nation's social and economic development. University students' performance should be a concern not only for administrators and educators but also for employers in the labor market. Academic achievement records are a key factor that employers consider when recruiting fresh graduates. Therefore, students must put in their best efforts to achieve strong academic results to meet the demands of prospective employers [31]

To sustain academic success in higher education, [32] identified past academic performance, self-efficacy beliefs, and behavioral engagement as the most significant predictors of students' achievement. Their findings suggest that students who are confident in their abilities and dedicate more time to studying tend to achieve better academic outcomes. Also, students from privileged backgrounds often attend high-quality schools, where they develop more advanced scholastic competencies, further enhancing their academic success. Additionally [33], as well as [34] emphasize the

importance of considering students' academic history, including previous assessment results, as these significantly influence their academic performance. Prior grades and class performance are strong predictors of academic success, as they shape students' learning habits and engagement. This finding suggests that academic performance tends to remain consistent throughout a student's educational journey. Those who develop strong study habits and perform well early in their academic careers are more likely to maintain high achievement levels. Conversely, students who struggle academically may continue to face challenges, potentially affecting their ability to succeed in both current and future coursework [29]. Based on these results and recommendations from other scholars regarding the importance of a strong academic background for higher education enrollment, we emphasize that higher grades in lower levels reflect stronger academic abilities, leading to better comprehension and performance in demanding courses. Additionally, students admitted with higher grades are more likely to demonstrate greater discipline and focus, which can further enhance overall academic success.

On the other hand, while many have recommended raising the entry requirements for diploma programs in health sciences based on Form Four results, some do not agree with this proposal. Specifically, 27.8% of tutors and a smaller portion of students (19.5%) oppose the idea. Their responses may be based on the argument that academic success is primarily influenced by factors beyond entry grades, such as personal motivation, effort, and the quality of institutional support available, as shown in Table 4. Reflecting on these findings, [35] as well as [36] emphasize that the academic achievement of any student is the result of a complex interplay of various factors, including study habits, personality traits, personal interests, college management attitudes and the teaching skills of the faculty members involved. The analysis reveals that factors such as the teaching efficacy of educators, study habits, distractions, and the family environment are significant predictors of college students' academic performance. These findings challenge the argument for increasing entry requirements for Health Science programs at NTA level 5 to 6, as the reality is that a student's success in university is influenced by many factors. If these factors are addressed along with the student's intrinsic motivation, a student with average Form Four grades could still perform well. Furthermore, if the majority's recommendations are considered, it is crucial for policymakers, parents, and health stakeholders in general to ask this important question: If entry requirements are increased, will they not exclude a large number of applicants who might have

succeeded under the current, relatively lower admission criteria?

In conclusion, the findings indicate a general support for increasing minimum entry qualifications, although opinions remain divided. Proponents argue that stronger academic backgrounds result in better preparedness and understanding, while the opposing view emphasizes the importance of personal effort, motivation, and external support systems, which may be just as critical. Policymakers and educators should carefully consider these differing perspectives when making decisions about entry requirements for health programs, ensuring that capable students are not excluded while still maintaining high academic standards.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, this study underscores that while Form Four examination performance is a significant predictor of academic success in health sciences non-degree programs, it is not the sole determinant of student outcomes. The findings reveal that other critical factors—such as personal commitment, study habits, teaching quality, and institutional support—also play pivotal roles in shaping academic performance. Students with Division I or II results from secondary school generally excel in diploma programs, while those with weaker academic backgrounds, particularly in subjects like Physics and Mathematics, may face challenges in the analytical and problem-solving aspects of their training. However, such students can still enhance their performance through motivation and effective study habits. College-level academic performance analysis indicates that while the majority of students attain a high GPA, a considerable proportion exhibit moderate to weak academic achievement. The strong correlations between motivation, study habits, and teaching quality further highlight the importance of non-academic factors in student success. Additionally, while Form Four results show moderate correlations with academic performance in college, institutional support alone does not guarantee success. The debate surrounding the potential increase in entry qualifications reveals that while many students and tutors advocate for stricter academic criteria, others argue that success is influenced by factors beyond entry grades. This study emphasizes that raising academic requirements without a balanced approach could exclude capable students who, with the right support systems, could thrive. Hence, solely focusing on academic criteria fails to address the broader factors that contribute to student success.

Moreover, based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to guide decisions on entry requirements for health programs,

ensuring that capable students are not excluded while maintaining high academic standards.

First, health sciences education governing boards, in collaboration with health training institutions, should introduce foundation courses for students with weaker academic backgrounds to enhance their preparedness before full admission into health programs.

Second, while higher entry requirements may enhance preparedness, admissions policies should also assess motivation, commitment, and study habits through a holistic approach, such as interviews or entrance exams, to identify capable students beyond their Form Four grades.

Third, health training institutions should strengthen academic resources, including libraries, tutoring programs, and mentorship opportunities, to support all students, especially those with weaker academic backgrounds.

Fourth, health training institutions should invest in continuous professional development for educators, equipping them with student-centered teaching methodologies that enhance engagement and learning outcomes.

Fifth, health training institutions should provide workshops and training on time management, study techniques, and academic discipline to help students develop effective learning habits.

Sixth, instead of excluding students with average Form Four results, institutions should implement bridging programs or academic support initiatives to help them adapt to the demands of health sciences training.

Seventh, policymakers should carefully assess both the benefits and potential drawbacks of raising entry requirements, ensuring that capable students are not unfairly excluded while maintaining high academic standards in health sciences education.

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